

Original article

Barriers to the Clinical Management of Viral Hepatitis in Pankshin LGA of Nigeria: Quantifying the Impact of Cost and Traditional Beliefs on Healthcare Access

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Abstract

Viral hepatitis remains a major global public health challenge, causing substantial morbidity and mortality, particularly from sequelae which include chronic hepatitis B and C infections, cirrhosis and primary liver cancer, despite the availability of effective vaccines and antiviral therapies. This study examined how economic constraints and socio-cultural beliefs shape awareness, knowledge, and treatment-seeking behaviour for viral hepatitis in Pankshin Local Government Area, north-central Nigeria. A community-based cross-sectional survey was conducted across eight communities using a structured questionnaire to collect data on hepatitis awareness, perceived causes, disease severity, treatment preferences, and barriers to clinical management. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze data collected. Overall awareness of hepatitis was very high (94.2%), with minimal variation by gender, education or community. However, detailed biomedical knowledge was limited, as most respondents recognised only hepatitis B and C, alongside persistent misconceptions regarding causation, including food, alcohol, and supernatural factors. Although hospital care was the preferred treatment option for most respondents (62.2%), a substantial proportion relied on herbal medicine (32.4%), particularly among those without formal education. High cost of care limited access to health facilities and perceived effectiveness of traditional remedies emerged as key barriers to clinical management, despite widespread optimism regarding curability (87.1%). These findings highlight a critical gap between awareness and effective engagement with clinical care. The study recommended decentralised hepatitis services, expanded affordable screening and vaccination, and culturally sensitive community-based interventions to address economic and belief-related barriers and improve hepatitis control in rural Nigeria.

Keywords: Viral Hepatitis, Rural Health, Treatment-Seeking Behaviour, Traditional Beliefs, Healthcare Access, Economic Barriers.

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Introduction

Viral hepatitis remains a major public health challenge globally. Viral hepatitis infects millions of people annually, causing significant morbidity and mortality. Chronic hepatitis B and C infections can cause liver damage that includes liver fibrosis, cirrhosis, hepatocellular carcinoma, and features of portal hypertension. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that 1.3 million people died due to hepatitis per year [1] and 1 in 3 people in the world have had infections with either HBV or HCV. Viral hepatitis can cause up to 1.4 million deaths annually, and HBV and HCV are responsible for about 90% of those deaths [2]. For most people, testing and treatment remain beyond reach and without urgent and sustained action, however, viral hepatitis is projected to cause an additional 9.5 million new infections, 2.1 million liver cancer cases, and 2.8 million deaths by 2030 [1].

Sub-Saharan Africa bears a disproportionate share of this burden, with population prevalence of chronic HBV infection frequently exceeding 8%, a level considered hyperendemic [3,4]. In Nigeria, a recent systematic review estimated a pooled HBV prevalence of 9.5%, rising to 10.7% in rural settings, underscoring the particularly heavy burden of infection outside urban centres [5]. Despite the availability of effective vaccination and antiviral therapy, diagnosis and treatment coverage across Africa remain alarmingly low, with fewer than 2% of people living with HBV diagnosed and only about 0.1% receiving treatment [4,6].

In response to this persistent burden, the World Health Organization's Global Health Sector Strategy on HIV, Viral Hepatitis and Sexually Transmitted Infections (2022–2030) outlines clear ambitious targets to eliminate viral hepatitis as a public health threat by 2030. The strategy aims to reduce new hepatitis infections to 520 000 cases annually and hepatitis-related deaths to 450 000 by 2030, which represents a 90% reduction in incidence and a 65% reduction in mortality compared to 2015. The strategy calls for substantial scale-up of hepatitis B vaccination, improved access to prevention, testing and treatment for hepatitis B and C, and targeted public education campaigns to raise awareness and reduce transmission [1,3,4]. However, progress toward these goals in many African countries, including Nigeria, is constrained by weak surveillance systems, limited diagnostic infrastructure, and inadequate domestic financing for hepatitis services [4,6]. Clinical management pathways are often based on complex treatment algorithms developed in high-income settings and rely on costly laboratory investigations such as HBV DNA testing, HBeAg assays, and fibrosis assessment. The centralisation of specialist care in tertiary hospitals further exacerbates access barriers for rural populations, where health facilities are fewer and transport costs are high [4,6-8].

Economic and structural constraints intersect with powerful social and cultural determinants that shape health-seeking behaviour. Among marginalised and low-income populations, utilisation of HBV services—including screening, vaccination, and treatment—often remains below 30%, with health system limitations, lack of insurance coverage, and socio-cultural factors such as discrimination, migration status, and precarious livelihoods influencing access [9]. Across diverse African contexts, studies consistently report limited knowledge of hepatitis, absence of a specific local term for the disease, widespread misconceptions about transmission, and high levels of stigma, all of which undermine screening uptake, disclosure, and long-term adherence to care [10-12].

In several African settings, traditional explanatory models of hepatitis further complicate engagement with biomedical care. In Ghana and Rwanda, chronic hepatitis is frequently attributed to spiritual causes, witchcraft, or “spiritual poison”, and severe liver disease is framed within local belief systems. These interpretations contribute to strong preferences for traditional or herbal healers, particularly when formal healthcare is perceived as costly, distant, or unresponsive [13-15]. Similar patterns have been documented in Burkina Faso, where established markets for traditional remedies, family influence, and medical pluralism divert patients away from formal care even after a positive diagnosis [3]. Community and provider reports from South Africa and Senegal further highlight how poverty, stigma, mistrust, long waiting times, and negative clinic experiences drive patients to seek care from traditional healers rather than biomedical facilities [4,8].

These intertwined economic, structural, and socio-cultural barriers are particularly salient in rural Nigeria, where HBV prevalence is high, health infrastructure is comparatively weaker, and poverty rates exceed those of urban areas [4-6]. While Nigeria-specific data on clinical management pathways and patient experiences in rural settings remain limited, regional evidence suggests that high direct medical costs including diagnostic tests and antiviral therapy alongside indirect costs such as transportation and lost income, are likely major determinants of poor access to care [3, 5-8,13]. In the absence of financial protection mechanisms, these costs can be prohibitive for rural households and contribute to delayed or discontinued care.

At the same time, traditional and religious belief systems, stigma, and limited awareness of hepatitis as a chronic but treatable infection strongly influence health-seeking behaviour in Nigeria, including reliance on traditional healers and herbal remedies [3,10,13,14,16,17]. Mixed-methods studies from West African populations, both within Africa and in diaspora settings, demonstrate that cultural norms, religious interpretations, family advice, and trust or lack thereof in biomedical services shape decisions around screening, long-term monitoring, and continuity of care [11,12,14,18,19].

Understanding how economic barriers and traditional belief systems jointly shape access to hepatitis services in rural Nigeria is therefore critical for designing effective and context-appropriate interventions. Quantifying the impact of costs covering diagnostics, treatment, transportation, and opportunity costs alongside measuring the influence of traditional explanatory models, stigma, and utilisation of traditional healers can help identify where patients are lost along the hepatitis care cascade and why [3,5,7-9,13,14]. Such evidence is urgently needed to inform Nigeria's contribution to regional strategies advocating decentralised and simplified treatment approaches, integration of hepatitis services into existing chronic disease and HIV platforms, and expansion of financial protection mechanisms for rural and low-income populations [4,6,20]. Accordingly, this study focuses on rural Nigerian communities to quantify the relative contributions of economic constraints and traditional beliefs to barriers in the clinical management of viral hepatitis and to generate evidence that can guide policy formulation, financing strategies, and culturally sensitive service delivery models.

This study therefore investigated how economic constraints and socio-cultural beliefs shape awareness, knowledge, and treatment-seeking behaviour for viral hepatitis; and also identified the key barriers to

effective clinical management in Pankshin Local Government Area of Nigeria.

Methodology

Study Design

This study employed a community-based cross-sectional survey to investigate the awareness, knowledge, and treatment-seeking behaviour for viral hepatitis in Pankshin Local Government Area, north-central Nigeria.

Study Area

This study was carried out in Eight communities - Kor, Kwalla, Mile 8, Nungwus, Kadyis, Jannaret, Dimmwai, Fumbis; each drawn from the following state wards - Belning, Wokkos, Fier, Lankan, Mukang-Nyelleng, Kangshu, Kangmun and Kasgong respectively, of Pankshin LGA in Plateau State of North-central Nigeria. Pankshin LGA lies approximately between latitude 9°18'–9°30' N and longitude 9°20'–9°35' E, with the administrative headquarters located in Pankshin town. Pankshin LGA covers an estimated land area of about 1,500 km² and is characterized by an undulating plateau landscape with rocky hills, valleys, and expansive farmlands. Its elevation on the Jos Plateau gives the area a relatively cool and temperate climate compared to much of northern Nigeria, with distinct wet and dry seasons that strongly influence agricultural and socioeconomic activities.

The area comprises a mix of semi-urban centers and predominantly rural settlements. Farming remains the backbone of the local economy, with crops such as maize, millet, rice, Irish potatoes, tomatoes, onions, and vegetables widely cultivated. Livestock rearing and petty trading complement farming as key livelihood activities. Periodic markets serve as important nodes for economic interaction between rural producers and urban consumers.

Pankshin LGA is culturally and ethnically diverse, inhabited mainly by the Ngas, Mupun, Miship, Tal, Fier, Kadung, Rom (Tambes) and Pai as the indigenous ethnic groups. The population practices Christianity, Islam, and African traditional religion, ATR. Its location, bordered by Mangu, Tafawa Balewa, Kanke, Langtang North, Mikang, Shendam and Qua'an Pan LGAs, enhances movement, trade, and social interaction across communities.

The diversity in settlement patterns, livelihoods, and environmental conditions across Pankshin LGA makes it a suitable setting for this study, providing a representative context for examining the research problem across both urban and rural populations within the same geographical space.

Area (LGA) who had resided in the area for at least ten (10) years and were willing to provide informed consent to participate in the study. Eight (8) communities within Pankshin LGA were selected. From each selected community, ten (10) respondents were purposively chosen based on eligibility criteria (age ≥18 years, minimum of 10 years' residence, and consent to participate). This resulted in a cumulative sample of 80 respondents across the eight communities.

Sampling Technique

A purposive sampling technique was employed. This approach was used to deliberately select participants who met the inclusion criteria and could provide rich, relevant information. The technique also ensured geographic and socio-cultural representation, as well as diversity in educational background, occupation, and gender across the selected communities.

Instrument for Data Collection

A structured questionnaire was designed to collect information on demographic characteristics, hepatitis awareness, perceived causes, disease severity, treatment preferences, and barriers to clinical management. The questionnaire was reviewed by experts in public health, epidemiology, and social sciences for **content and face validity**, ensuring relevance, clarity, and cultural appropriateness of items.

Reliability Testing

The reliability of the questionnaire was assessed using the test-retest method. The instrument was administered to a subset of 10 respondents in a pilot community, and repeated after two weeks. Responses from the two administrations were compared using Pearson correlation coefficient, yielding a high correlation ($r \geq 0.85$), indicating strong reliability and stability of the instrument over time.

Data Collection Procedure

Trained field assistants administered the questionnaire on the spot. Geographical coordinates of each respondent's household were recorded using eTrex 10 GPS units to enable spatial analysis. The coordinates were later imported into ArcGIS for mapping and visualisation of research sites and community distribution.

Data Analysis

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analysed using the latest version of R statistical software (version 4.5.2). Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means) summarised respondents' characteristics and responses. Comparative analyses across demographic and spatial categories were performed using chi-square tests or Fisher's exact test where appropriate. GIS mapping in ArcGIS (ArcGIS Pro version 3.6) enabled visualisation of the spatial distribution of awareness, treatment-seeking patterns, and barriers to care across the study communities.

Results

Figure 2: Response of People on Hepatitis Awareness in Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 1: The Map Showing the Study Area: Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Study Population and Sampling

The study population comprised adult residents aged 18 years and above living in selected communities of Pankshin Local Government

Figure 3: Knowledge of People on Types of Hepatitis in Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 6: Understanding of the Fatal Nature of Hepatitis Among the Rural Communities in Pankshin LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 4: Knowledge of Hepatitis Among People Within the 8 Rural Communities of Pankshin LGA in Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 7: Views of People on the Serious Impact of Hepatitis Disease in Their Communities in Pankshin LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 5: Views Of Respondents on Causes of Hepatitis in Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 8: Common Treatment Options for Hepatitis in Rural Communities of Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 9: Reasons For Preference of Alternative Hepatitis Treatment (Traditional Medicine, Prayer or Spiritual Solution) Among 8 Rural Communities in Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 12: Responses of People on the Challenges they Face in Prevention/Treatment of Hepatitis in Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 10: Responses of People's Belief on The Curability of Hepatitis in Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 11: Education- Based Responses of People's Belief on The Curability of Hepatitis in Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Awareness and Knowledge of Viral Hepatitis

Overall awareness of hepatitis was very high, with **94.2%** of respondents reporting that they had heard of the disease (Figure. 2, 3 and 4). Awareness did not differ significantly by gender, educational level, or community of residence, although slightly lower awareness was observed in Fumbis. This suggests that hepatitis information is widely disseminated through community networks rather than being strongly dependent on formal education or demographic characteristics. Despite high general awareness, specific biomedical knowledge was limited (Figure. 3). Hepatitis B (HBV) and Hepatitis C (HCV) were the most commonly recognized viral types, while awareness of Hepatitis D and E was very low. A substantial proportion of respondents could not identify any hepatitis type, indicating a gap between general disease recognition and detailed clinical understanding.

Perceived Causes and Misconceptions

Most respondents (60.0%) correctly identified viral infection as the cause of hepatitis (Figure. 5). However, misconceptions persisted: 22.4% attributed hepatitis to contaminated food or water, 11.8% to alcohol consumption, 4.7% to witchcraft, and 1.2% to promiscuity. Correct identification of viral etiology was more common among respondents with tertiary education, although statistical testing was limited by sparse cell counts, preventing valid Chi-square inference across education, gender, and community categories.

Community Exposure and Perceived Severity

Personal exposure to hepatitis was widespread, with 93.0% of respondents reporting that they knew someone who had suffered from or died of hepatitis (Figure. 5). While awareness was consistently high across education and gender, significant variation was observed across communities, with universal reporting in several locations and lower exposure awareness in Fumbis and Kadyis.

Perceptions of disease severity were mixed (Figure. 6 and 7). Although 58.1% of respondents described hepatitis as "serious" or "very serious," 41.9% perceived it as "mild" or "not a problem." No statistically significant differences were detected by education or gender, suggesting that risk perception is uneven but broadly distributed across demographic groups.

Treatment-Seeking Behaviour and Alternative Care

Formal healthcare facilities were the preferred source of treatment for 62.2% of respondents, particularly among those with secondary education (Figure. 8). Nevertheless, a substantial proportion (32.4%)

relied on herbal medicine, with use exceeding hospital care among respondents with no formal education. Differences by education were observed but were not statistically significant.

Motivations for alternative treatment varied spatially (Figure. 9). Perceived effectiveness was the dominant reason across most communities, while cost was particularly important in Fumbis and Nungwus, and lack of hospital access was most prominent in Kor. These patterns highlight the combined influence of belief systems, economic constraints, and geographic access on treatment decisions.

Perceived Curability and Structural Barriers

Optimism regarding hepatitis outcomes was high, with 87.1% of respondents believing that hepatitis can be cured (Figure. 10). This belief was consistent across education, gender, and communities. However, respondents identified several systemic barriers to effective management, notably high cost of care, poor awareness, limited vaccination, and inadequate access to health facilities (Figure. 11-12). Free-response analysis reinforced these findings, with lack of awareness (33.3%) and poor vaccination uptake (16.2%) emerging as the most frequently cited challenges, followed by access and cost-related barriers. Collectively, these responses highlight a tension between biomedical preferences and socio-economic constraints shaping hepatitis care pathways.

Discussion

The Hepatitis disease Awareness–Knowledge Paradox

This study revealed a generally high level of awareness of hepatitis among respondents, with more than ninety percent of the respondents indicating that they had heard of the disease. Knowledge of hepatitis was consistently high across education levels, genders, and communities, suggesting that awareness of the disease is widespread within the study area. The minimal differences observed among respondents with no formal education, primary, secondary, and tertiary education indicate that hepatitis awareness may not be strongly dependent on formal schooling. Instead, information may be disseminated through community interactions, health campaigns, media, or prior exposure to health services.

Similarly, awareness of hepatitis did not differ substantially between males and females, implying equitable access to health information across genders. This finding is encouraging, as gender-based disparities in health knowledge can negatively affect disease prevention and health-seeking behaviour. The high level of awareness observed among both genders suggests that public health messaging related to hepatitis has reached a broad audience.

Across the various communities studied, awareness of hepatitis was also uniformly high, although small variations were observed in a few locations. These minor differences may be attributable to variations in local health outreach activities or access to healthcare facilities. Nevertheless, the overall pattern indicates that hepatitis is a well-recognised health issue across the study area. Despite the high level of general awareness, findings from questions assessing specific knowledge of hepatitis types suggest that understanding may be limited to a few commonly known forms, particularly hepatitis B and C, while awareness of other types remains low. This highlights an important gap between general awareness and detailed knowledge, underscoring the need for targeted health education programmes that emphasise the different types of hepatitis, their modes of transmission, prevention, and health consequences.

The findings suggest that while awareness of hepatitis is high, public health efforts should shift from basic awareness creation to improving comprehensive knowledge and promoting preventive practices within the population. Despite this high general awareness, specific biomedical knowledge was limited (Figure. 3). Hepatitis B (HBV) and Hepatitis C

(HCV) were the most commonly recognized viral types, while knowledge of Hepatitis D and E was very low. A substantial proportion of respondents were unable to identify any specific viral type, indicating a gap between general disease recognition and clinical understanding.

This study reveals a clear awareness–knowledge paradox in rural communities of Pankshin LGA. Although nearly all respondents had heard of hepatitis, detailed understanding of viral types, transmission pathways, and clinical management remained limited. Similar patterns have been reported across sub-Saharan Africa, where general disease recognition coexists with incomplete biomedical knowledge and persistent misinformation [10-12]. The continued attribution of hepatitis to food, alcohol, or supernatural causes reflects the coexistence of biomedical and non-biomedical explanatory models, consistent with findings from Ghana, Rwanda, and Burkina Faso [3,13,15].

Economic Constraints and Informal Treatment Pathways

Cost emerged as a dominant structural barrier to hepatitis care, shaping treatment-seeking behaviour even among respondents who preferred hospital-based care. High costs of diagnostics, treatment, transport, and opportunity losses act as a structural filter, redirecting patients toward herbal medicine and other informal pathways, as reported elsewhere in Africa [4,6,7]. The reliance on perceived effectiveness of herbal treatments reported across multiple communities reinforces informal care pathways that may delay diagnosis and sustained viral suppression, potentially maintaining community-level transmission [3,4].

Spatial Inequalities and Access Barriers

Significant variation across communities highlights the role of spatial and infrastructural inequalities. In communities such as Kor, physical access to hospitals was a dominant barrier, reflecting broader patterns of landscape epidemiology in rural Africa, where decentralised services remain limited and specialist care is concentrated in urban centres [6,8].

The Curability Paradox and Clinical Literacy

The widespread belief in hepatitis curability represents a double-edged sword. While optimism may encourage care-seeking, it may also reinforce reliance on non-clinical treatments if traditional remedies are perceived as curative. This finding underscores the need to move beyond awareness campaigns toward clinical literacy, emphasising that although hepatitis is treatable, effective management requires diagnosis, monitoring, vaccination, and long-term biomedical care [4,6]. The findings demonstrate that hepatitis care in rural Nigeria is shaped by the intersection of knowledge gaps, economic constraints, belief systems, and spatial access. Addressing these challenges will require decentralised service delivery, integration of hepatitis care into existing primary health platforms, improved vaccine access, and culturally sensitive community engagement that builds trust in biomedical care while acknowledging local explanatory models [3,14,20].

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that while awareness of hepatitis is very high in rural communities of Pankshin Local Government Area, this awareness does not translate into comprehensive biomedical knowledge, accurate risk perception, or optimal health-seeking behaviour. The findings reveal a persistent awareness–knowledge gap, characterized by limited understanding of hepatitis types, ongoing misconceptions about causation, and mixed perceptions of disease severity. Although most respondents preferred hospital-based care and expressed strong optimism regarding hepatitis curability, economic constraints, geographic barriers, and entrenched belief systems continue to redirect many individuals toward herbal and informal treatment pathways. Community-level variations in exposure, access, and treatment preferences further highlight the influence of spatial inequalities on hepatitis management. Together, these results indicate that hepatitis control in rural Nigeria is constrained not only by

healthcare system limitations but also by socio-economic realities and cultural interpretations of disease.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, hepatitis interventions in rural settings should move beyond basic awareness campaigns toward strengthening clinical literacy, emphasizing accurate knowledge of viral transmission, prevention, vaccination, and the need for diagnosis and long-term biomedical management. Policies should prioritize the decentralisation of hepatitis services, integrating screening, vaccination, and treatment into primary healthcare and existing chronic disease platforms to reduce cost and access barriers. Financial protection mechanisms, including subsidised diagnostics and treatment, are essential to limit diversion to informal care. In addition, culturally sensitive community engagement strategies that involve traditional leaders and informal care providers can help address misconceptions while fostering trust in formal healthcare services. Finally, targeted outreach to underserved communities with limited facility access is critical to reducing spatial inequities and achieving effective hepatitis prevention and control in rural Nigeria.

References

- [1] World Health Organization. Hepatitis. Geneva: WHO; 2020 Mar 11. Available from: <https://www.who.int/health-topics/hepatitis>
- [2] Grant LM, Purres M. Viral hepatitis. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Mar 10. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK554549/>
- [3] Giles-Vernick T, Hejoaka F, Sanou A, Shimakawa Y, Bamba I, Traore A. Barriers to linkage to care for hepatitis B virus infection: a qualitative analysis in Burkina Faso, West Africa. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2016;95(6):1368–1375. doi:10.4269/ajtmh.16-0398
- [4] Lemoine M, Eholie S, Lacombe K. Reducing the neglected burden of viral hepatitis in Africa: strategies for a global approach. *J Hepatol.* 2015;62(2):469–476. doi:10.1016/j.jhep.2014.10.008
- [5] Ajuwon B, Yujuico I, Roper K, Richardson A, Sheel M, Lidbury B. Hepatitis B virus infection in Nigeria: a systematic review and meta-analysis of data published between 2010 and 2019. *BMC Infect Dis.* 2021;21(1):1114. doi:10.1186/s12879-021-06800-6
- [6] Spearman CW, Andersson MI, Bright B, Dawwar P, Desalegn H, Guingané A, Johannessen A, Kabagambe K, Lemoine M, Matthews PC, Ndow G, Riches N, Shimakawa Y, Sombié R, Stockdale AJ, Taljaard J, Vinikoor MJ, Wandeler G, Okeke E, Sonderup MW. A new approach to prevent, diagnose, and treat hepatitis B in Africa. *BMC Glob Public Health.* 2023;1:26. doi:10.1186/s44263-023-00026-1
- [7] Chabrol F, Noah N, Tchoumi E, Vidal L, Kuaban C, Carrieri MP, Boyer S. Screening, diagnosis and care cascade for viral hepatitis B and C in Yaoundé, Cameroon: a qualitative study of patients and health providers coping with uncertainty and unbearable costs. *BMJ Open.* 2019;9(3):e025415. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2018-025415
- [8] Coste M, Diouf A, Ndong C, Diouf A, Périères L, Nishimwe M, Bureau M, Ndiaye A, Maradan G, Diallo A, Boyer S. Investigating linkage to care following community-based screening for hepatitis B virus in rural Senegal: a mixed methods study. *J Viral Hepat.* 2024;31(5):544–556. doi:10.1111/jvh.13977
- [9] Li C, Thapa D, Mi Q, Gao Y, Fu X. Disparities in hepatitis B virus healthcare service access among marginalised poor populations: a mixed-method systematic review. *Infect Dis Poverty.* 2024;13(1):25. doi:10.1186/s40249-024-01225-0
- [10] Mokaya J, McNaughton AL, Burbridge L, Maponga T, O'Hara G, Andersson M, Seeley J, Matthews PC. A blind spot? Confronting the stigma of hepatitis B virus infection: a systematic review. *Wellcome Open Res.* 2018;3:29. doi:10.12688/wellcomeopenres.14273.2
- [11] Mitchell T, Nayagam J, Dusheiko G, Agarwal K. Health inequalities in the management of chronic hepatitis B virus infection in patients from sub-Saharan Africa in high-income countries. *JHEP Rep.* 2023;5(1):100623. doi:10.1016/j.jhepr.2022.100623
- [12] Freeland C, Bodor S, Perera U, Cohen C. Barriers to hepatitis B screening and prevention for African immigrant populations in the United States: a qualitative study. *Viruses.* 2020;12(3):305. doi:10.3390/v12030305
- [13] Adjei C, Stutterheim SE, Naab F, Ruiters RAC. Barriers to chronic hepatitis B treatment and care in Ghana: a qualitative study with people with hepatitis B and healthcare providers. *PLoS One.* 2019;14(12):e0225830. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0225830
- [14] Adjei C, Ampem K, Dzansi G, Tenkorang-Twum D, Klutse K. Health-seeking behavior of persons with chronic hepatitis B in peri-urban Ghana: application of the Health Belief Model. *SAGE Open.* 2024;14(2):21582440241254167. doi:10.1177/21582440241254167
- [15] Van Nuil JI, Shumbusho F, Kateera F, Mukuralinda A, Kabahizi J, Muvunyi C, Musabeyezu E, Mukabatsinda C, Mbituyumuremi A, Nsanzimana S, Mukherjee J, Gupta N. Care seeking and treatment for hepatitis C infection in Rwanda: a qualitative study of patient experiences. *Glob Public Health.* 2020;15(12):1778–1788. doi:10.1080/17441692.2020.1801787
- [16] Ngwenya B, Anderson M, Mpanza N, Mbokazi W, Zuma L, Khoza T, Sukali G, Waddilove E, Delphin M, Iwuji C, Mhlongo N, Majosi N, Seeley J, Upton J, Harling G, Matthews PC, Edwards A. Community dialogue to enhance understanding of beliefs, behaviours and barriers to care for people living with liver disease and HBV infection in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. *J Virus Erad.* 2024;10:100378. doi:10.1016/j.jve.2024.100378
- [17] Mugisha J, Mokaya J, Bukonya D, Ssembajja F, Mayambala D, Newton R, Matthews PC, Seeley J. Knowledge, experience, and beliefs about hepatitis B virus infection in South Western Uganda. *Front Public Health.* 2019;7:304. doi:10.3389/fpubh.2019.00304
- [18] Coe J, Birnbaum J, Omarufilo F, Sigal S, Akiyama M. Out of sight, into mind: a socioecological model-informed qualitative study on barriers and facilitators to hepatitis B care among West African immigrants in the Bronx, New York. *BMC Public Health.* 2024;24:20358. doi:10.1186/s12889-024-20358-3
- [19] Block S, Zovich B, Borondy-Jenkins F, Chen T, Moraras K, Anshah B, Cohen C. Exploring the psychosocial influences on hepatitis B and liver cancer disparities. *J Racial Ethn Health Disparities.* 2025. doi:10.1007/s40615-025-02580-w
- [20] Nyama E, Allan-Blitz LT, Bitwayiki R, Swaray M, Lebbie W, Lavalie D, Mhango M, Gupta N, Rodriguez M. Challenges of hepatitis B treatment in rural sub-Saharan Africa: treatment initiation and outcomes from a public hospital-based clinic in Kono, Sierra Leone. *J Viral Hepat.* 2023;30(7):455–462. doi:10.1111/jvh.13812